

Research Topic: Beyond Push-Pull: Emotional Ambivalence and Digital Networks in Nigerian Teachers' Migration Intentions

Target participants: Nigerian Secondary School Teachers

Number of FGDs: Two (Recruit 6 public and 6 private secondary school teachers per group (2 groups) = 12 teachers. Schedule the FGDs on different days/times. This stratification was designed to create a conducive environment for open discussion of sector-specific experiences.)

Estimated duration: 65–90 minutes

Moderator: Researcher

Recording: Audio (with consent)

PART A: Focus Group Discussion Guide

Introduction (Moderator Script)

Thank you all for agreeing to participate. This discussion is about your experiences and views as secondary school teachers in Nigeria, particularly regarding international relocation in the digital era. The focus group will last approximately 65–90 minutes.

There are no right or wrong answers. Kindly respect different opinions from your colleagues. We are interested in your honest opinions. Please speak one at a time so the recorder can pick up all voices. Please feel free to speak openly and allow others to contribute as well. Everything you share will be confidential.

Before we begin, I want to confirm that you all signed the consent form. Does anyone have any questions before we start?

Participation is voluntary. You may choose not to answer any question or leave the discussion at any time without any consequences.

Opening Question: Can you tell me a little about your teaching journey? What subject/level do you teach, and for how long?

Main Interview Question: As teachers, what are your thoughts or feelings about the possibility of moving abroad to teach?

Probes

- Can you recall a specific moment or reason that made you consider this idea?
- How do you view the life of Nigerian teachers who have moved abroad? What images or stories come to mind?

- What experiences in your teaching career have shaped your thoughts about relocating to teaching abroad?
- What are the biggest motivations or deterrents for you when it comes to moving to teaching abroad?
- In what ways have the internet and social media influenced your awareness or feelings about teaching opportunities in other countries?
- Was there a particular moment that sparked your interest in relocating abroad to teach?
- How do your colleagues impact your thoughts on the idea of teaching abroad?
- How tangible does the idea of relocating abroad to teach feel to you right now—does it seem very possible or just a distant thought?
- If you had to rank your reasons for considering relocation, what would be at the top? Is it for professional growth, personal safety, financial reasons, or something else entirely?

Others

- Is there anything about relocating that excites you but also makes you anxious?
- Is there anything else you would like to add that we have not covered?

Closing Reminder

Thank you all for your time and honesty. Remember, what is shared here stays here. Please respect each other's privacy. If you have any questions after this discussion, please feel free to contact me using the information on the participant information sheet.